

imine nitrogen atom of the 1,2-dimethylethane-1,2-dionedi-hydrazone and the terminal NH_2 groups coordinating to the neighbouring metal ions. As the bis-hydrazone complexes could not form any additional complex having the stoichiometry MLX_3 , the possibility of the complexes to possess the structure 1(a) is thus eliminated. Further evidence in support of structure 1(b) comes from the electronic spectral data.

The nickel(II) complexes having magnetic moment values in the range 3.00-3.15 B. M. manifest nearly octahedral coordination of ligand atoms about nickel(II) ions with $^3\text{A}_{2g}$ ground state under octahedral geometry or more precisely $^3\text{B}_{1g}$ under D_{4h} symmetry.

The spectra of the complexes show two bands in the region $14000\text{-}19000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a third band at $\sim 24000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These resemble the spectral features of NiL_2X_3 complexes implying that all the metal ion centres have similar ligand fields. Similar ligand fields would arise provided the complexes possess a polymeric structure 1(b) wherein each metal ion is coordinated to two imine nitrogen atoms and two NH_2 groups from the two adjacent molecules rather than the structure 1(a) wherein each bis-complex functions as ligands and bonding to metal ions on either side as an exo-bi-bidentate ligand. The structure 1(a) is expected to have two kinds of ligand fields about the metal ions and consequently the split components of the orbitally triplets in an octahedral field will have different energies leading to a larger number of electronic transitions as compared to the structure 1(b). The observed spectral data showing only three bands in the ligand field region lead us to believe that the complexes may have the structure 1(b). The three bands in the electronic spectra of the complexes are attributed to the transitions,

The cobalt(II) complexes possess magnetic moment values in the range 5.00-5.20 B.M. which correspond to an octahedral stereochemistry about the metal ion having the ground state ^4F which splits into $^4\text{T}_{1g}$, $^4\text{T}_{2g}$ and $^4\text{A}_{2g}$ whose energy levels increase successively and ^4P terms transforming as $^4\text{T}_{1g}$ under D_{4h} symmetry. One of the important features of the electronic spectra of the complexes is the appearance of a strong charge-transfer band above 20000 cm^{-1} and has in a few cases impeded resolution of the spectra in this region.

Though electronic spectra of several cobalt(II) complexes have been reported⁶⁻¹¹, their assignments have not been unambiguous. The ligand field transitions, $^4\text{A}_{2g} \leftarrow ^4\text{T}_{1g}$ and $^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P}) \leftarrow ^4\text{T}_{1g}$ appear in the visible region of spectra, the former being always weak, is scarcely observed. On the other hand, the latter appears as a relatively intense band with some amount of structure. The present cobalt(II) complexes exhibit a multiplet band

structure in the region $16000\text{-}19000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the band width spreading over *ca.* 3000 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to the transition $^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P}) \leftarrow ^4\text{T}_{1g}$. It may further be pointed out that the spectral features have similarity to the spectra of the bis-complexes, CoL_2X_3 implying similar ligand fields about the cobalt(II) ions providing evidence in favour of the structure 1(b) and ruling out the possibility of structure 1(a).

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Infrared Studies of Some Metal Periodates*

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PERIODATE ion is a very good oxidising and stabilizing agent. It can stabilize the unusual oxidation states of many transition metal ions. Very often periodates give insoluble compounds making them unsuitable for X-ray crystallographic studies. In these cases infrared study is very useful to characterise the bondings. In this attempt we have studied some periodate compounds of

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iron(III), cobalt(III) nickel(IV), cerium(IV), uranium(VI) and gallium(III). Only cobalt compound is water soluble and the rest are insoluble. It is only very recently that a periodate compound of cobalt has been studied by X-ray crystallographic method⁴.

Experimental

Cobalt(III) and iron(III) compounds were prepared following the methods outlined in the literature¹⁻³. Chemical analyses confirmed their composition and formulated as $\text{Na}_5[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6)_2(\text{OH})_2] \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{H}_3[\text{Co}_4\text{I}_3\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_{12}] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Na}_5[\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6)_2(\text{OH})_2] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{H}_3[\text{Fe}_4\text{I}_3\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_{12}]$.

Uranyl compound: To a hot (below 80°) solution of $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 g in 25 ml water) a 75 ml solution containing potassium hydroxide (12 g) and KIO_4 (1.4 g) was added with vigorous stirring for 5-10 min. The mixture was then allowed to settle and filtered. To the bright yellow filtrate lithium sulphate solution was added. The resulting light yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with water until the pH of the final washing reached 8. It was further washed with absolute ethanol followed by ether, dried over CaCl_2 and then analysed. The empirical formula of the compound was found to be $\text{Li}_{1.6}[\text{UO}_2\text{I}_6\text{O}_{30}] \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Cerium compound: Ceric ammonium nitrate (1 g) was dissolved in distilled water (10 ml) previously acidified with conc. HNO_3 , and filtered. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 1.15-1.50 and then mixed with a solution of NaIO_4 (2 g in 30 ml water). A yellow solid obtained was filtered, washed thoroughly to free it from cerium and then dissolved in KOH solution (3N) by the addition of requisite amount of NaIO_4 . To the resulting solution a concentrated solution of sodium nitrate was added and a light yellow precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with water followed by methanol until free from alkali, cerium nitrate and periodate. The product was dried over conc. H_2SO_4 and analysed. The empirical formula of the compound was found to be $\text{NaCeIO}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Nickel compound: $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution (2 g in 10 ml water) was added to KOH solution (50 ml, 4N) containing KIO_4 (1 g). Potassium persulphate (5 g) was added to the solution and stirred for ~3 h. A brown solution obtained was filtered. To the filtrate an equivalent amount of lithium sulphate solution was added. The resulting brown precipitate was filtered, washed with water to free it from alkali and other impurities, followed by ether and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator. On analysis the empirical formula of the compound was found to be $\text{Li}_2[\text{NiI}_6\text{O}_{24}] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Gallium compounds: (i) Gallium sulphate (0.0093 mol) solution was added to KIO_4 (0.02 mol) in KOH solution (3N). The mixture was stirred for 4 h with slow heating. The solution obtained was filtered and an equivalent amount of lithium sulphate solution was added to the filtrate. The

white precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with alcohol (1 : 1) and finally with water to free it from alkali, lithium periodate and other impurities. The product was further washed with ethanol and air dried. On analysis the empirical formula of the compound was found to be $\text{Li}_7[\text{Ga}(\text{IO}_6)_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

(ii) Gallium sulphate (0.0117 mol in 25 ml water) was stirred with an equivalent amount of NaIO_4 in water for 2-3 h. pH of the solution was 3-4. The white precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol (1 : 1), dried and analysed. The compound was found to be $\text{Ga}_5(\text{IO}_6)_8 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer in the CsI phase.

Results and Discussion

The compounds can be divided apparently into three categories : simple salts, simple complexes, and polymerised or condensed complexes. But it has not been possible to classify them under the above categories only from their infrared studies. All these compounds show peaks more or less in the same region, with occasional shifting of the peak positions consistent with change in molecular weight of the compounds as well as environment of the characteristic groups (Table 1).

Strong and broad ir bands have been found at $3600\text{-}2600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (OH). Broadening of the bands suggest hydrogen bonding of the type O-H...O. Deformation vibrations of the water molecules appear at $1650\text{-}1575\text{ cm}^{-1}$. A large number of absorptions are observed at $1380\text{-}1035\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as a result of I-OH deformation. Expected peaks due to M-OH deformation in the compounds (2) and (4) seem to overlap with that of I-OH deformation, because M-OH are generally obtained in this range⁶. At the lower range (below 850 cm^{-1}) complicated bands are observed for most of the compounds. Peaks at $770\text{-}550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to I-O stretching vibrations. Some authors⁷ observed a band with various peaks at $590\text{-}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to δ_{OH} . It is rather difficult to distinguish between $\nu_{\text{I-O}}$ and δ_{OH} .

Several peaks at $530\text{-}215\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are probably due to O-I-O deformations. Metal-oxygen vibrations may also appear in this region⁸⁻¹⁰. It is, however, difficult to distinguish the bands in this region. Probability of the I-O-I bond present in the compound (5) is supported by the peaks 600 and 450 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to I-O-I stretching and bending modes, respectively⁸.

Regarding additional peaks, 880 cm^{-1} for compound (7) can be assigned to $\text{U}=\text{O}$, and 940 cm^{-1} for (9) is probably due to OH deformation. Additional peak at 850 cm^{-1} in case of (1) can be assigned to Fe-O-Fe bridging. Other peaks are difficult to characterise.

TABLE 1—IR SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS (cm⁻¹)

Sl. no.	Compounds	ν_{OH}	δ_{I-OH}	δ_{H_2O}	δ_{I-OH}	ν_{I-O}	$\tau_{I-O(H)}$	ν_{I-O-I}	δ_{O-I-O}	δ_{I-O-I}	Additional peaks
1.	H ₂ [Fe ₂ I ₂ O ₈ .H ₁₂]	3410-3490s,b	-	1650m	1360w	687m,b	-	-	500vs 420s 300s 230m 220m 475s 400s 255m 235m 215m	-	850m
2.	Na ₂ [Fe(H ₂ IO ₆) ₂ (OH) ₂].6H ₂ O	3540 3480 3400vs	2250w	1635, 1615m	1380w 1150w 1015sh	615s	-	-	475s 400s 255m 235m 215m	-	-
3.	H ₂ [Co ₂ I ₂ O ₈ .H ₁₂].6H ₂ O	3350-2600	2230 v,w	1530m	1130w 1080w	780s 670m 575m 550m	-	-	475m 350s 290sh 275sh	-	-
4.	Na ₂ [Co(H ₂ IO ₆) ₂ (OH) ₂].8H ₂ O	3600-3100s,b	2260w	1610-1595m	1300m 1270w 1165sh 1080w	770s 720w 630w	880w	-	530w,b 390w 340w 320w 300w 255sh	-	-
5.	Li ₂ [NiI ₂ O ₈].6H ₂ O	3500-3360s,b	-	1650m	-	710m,b	-	600w	-	450m,b	-
6.	NaCeIO ₆ .H ₂ O	3380-3110s,b	2380m	1600-1575w,b	1460w	700-670s,b]	-	-	450-420m,b 370vw 210m,s	-	-
7.	Li ₁₀ [UO ₂ I ₂ O ₈].8H ₂ O	3400s,b	2200w	1640w,b	1390m	720-650vs,b	-	-	480-400vs,b 285w 220w 310sh 235w 215w	-	880m
8.	Li ₇ [Ga(IO ₆) ₂].4H ₂ O	3520-3430m	-	1640w,b	-	700s 620s	-	-	480s 385m 290s 250m	-	-
9.	Ga ₂ (IO ₆) ₂ .H ₂ O	3500-3080s,b	2320w	1625-1600m,b	1380s 1170-1035w,b	720-650m,b	-	-	480s 385m 290s 250m	-	940w

vs = very strong, s = strong, m = medium, sh = shoulder, b = broad, vw = very weak.

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Synthesis and Studies on Some Mixed-Metal Periodates of Cerium(IV)

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MIXED metal periodates of the type M^IM^{IV}IO₆ (M^I=Na, K, NH₄, Rb, Cs, and M^{IV}=Ni, Mn, Pb, Ce, Sn) are known¹⁻⁴. Periodate of nickel(IV) was first prepared¹ followed² by Ni^{IV} and Mn^{IV}. The compounds of lead, germanium and